

Inferential online measurement of 3D fractal dimension of fluidized bed spray agglomerates

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A model-based approach is presented to obtain 3D information about the morphology of agglomerates produced in spray fluidized beds. The two-step approach combines high detail information from X-ray tomography with easy and fast to obtain information about single agglomerate shape descriptor. Evaluation of the approach is performed with respect to image-based online data; areas of improvement of the approach are discussed.

Keywords: agglomeration; fluidized bed; image analysis; morphology; structure

Introduction

Spray agglomeration in fluidized beds is a common technology to formulate bulk powders from individual particles. Applications can be found, for example, in the formulation of multi-component fertilizers, complex solids-based pharmaceutical formulations and in food industry, especially in the formulation of food powders with instant properties (Palzer 2011).

In spray agglomeration (see Fig. 1), an initial bulk material is sprayed with a liquid-based binding agent, e.g., a polymer solution. Binder droplets deposit on the surface of the particles, wetting a fraction of it. If particles contact at wetted surface areas (either dry-wet or wet-wet contacts), a liquid bridge is formed, the geometry of which depends on the available liquid volume, its surface tension, and the contact angle between the binder solution and the particle surface. The liquid bridge can transfer momentum between the contacting particles, establishing a joint movement as a single structure (an agglomerate). If the liquid bridge solidifies, a solid bridge forms, establishing a stronger bond between the contacting particles. Fluidization of the bulk material enables mixing of the particles, i.e., allowing for droplet deposition on the surface of all particles, and provides the necessary heat for solidification of the liquid

bridges, e.g., by removing excess liquid, initiating crystallization of a dissolved solid component within the binder.

Product properties, e.g., rehydration behavior of food powders or active area of catalyst pellets, strongly correlate with agglomerate morphology, for example, the number of primary particles combined into an agglomerate, number and strength of individual solid bridges between primary particles within the agglomerate, or the porosity of the formed agglomerate. In terms of rehydration behavior, too small and too dense agglomerates will not dissolve quickly as the liquid cannot penetrate the pore space. If the agglomerate is too large, penetration of liquid into the interior of the agglomerate is hindered by the tortuosity and total length of the formed pores.

One key morphological indicator to describe the internal structure, e.g., the pore space, and many usage properties (e.g., mechanical strength and rehydration behavior), is the fractal dimension of an agglomerate (Dadkhah et al. 2012).

To enable formulation of preferential agglomerate structures (e.g., fractal dimension), especially by model-based process control, information on agglomerate structure formation must be accessible on process-relevant time scale, i.e., information must be obtained fast enough such that appropriate reaction (controller action) can be realized. In spray fluidized beds, agglomerate formation is achieved typically within minutes.

This requirement rules out most of the techniques commonly used for the characterization of agglomerates, for instance scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Bahramian 2019, Düsenberg et al. 2023, Furuviik et al. 2022), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (De Temmermann et al. 2012, LaRocca et al. 2015), X-ray computed tomography (XCT; Dadkhah et al. 2012, Farber et al 2003, Pashminehazar et al. 2016) or optical coherence tomography (OCT; Campello et al. 2014, Dong et al.

2017, Koukoulas et al 2012), due to time-consuming sample preparation and typical off-site location of the devices. TEM, XCT and OCT are further limited in the number of objects that can be studied in parallel, making difficult the transfer of information from small samples (low number of objects) to the properties of the bulk material. The main advantage of these methods is the high level of detail of structure information that can be extracted from individual objects (agglomerates), often directly in all three spatial dimensions.

An alternative approach is the use of image-based techniques with inline and online capabilities, i.e., using a high-speed optical camera setup to obtain image sequences of particles during the formulation processes. These setups are used routinely for sizing of individual particles, by means of commercial equipment that is either installed directly into the apparatus or utilizes a particle side-stream (e.g., Camsizer by MicrotracRetsch, or Quickpic by Sympatec).

Especially in case of dense particulate systems like fluidized beds, the at-line operation is advantageous. Bulk information on particle size is obtained in minutes, but this may still be too slow to track the dynamics of agglomerate formation. The speed in measurement is countered by a lower level of detail with respect to structure information (two-dimensional information, cf. Silva et al. 2013, Naidu et al. 2017).

So far, no concept that addresses the online measurement of 3D fractal dimension of agglomerates in spray fluidized beds has been developed and evaluated. This limits the control of spray agglomeration processes towards specific structures and bulk material properties, leading to off-spec products that need to be recycled or discarded.

In this work, we present and evaluate a model-based concept for online characterization of 3D fractal dimension of agglomerates produced in spray fluidized beds, closing this methodological gap.

The contribution is structured as follows: Next, the development of the model-based assessment procedure is described. This is followed by the presentation of a number of selected results obtained from the evaluation of online data. The contribution closes with the main conclusions and an outlook on future work.

Development of the inferential assessment procedure

In the following, we describe the whole development process to obtain the online capable assessment of 3D fractal dimension of spray agglomerates. The assessment procedure combines two models that establish a link between an easy and fast to obtain shape factor of an agglomerate to its 3D fractal dimension.

First, we present briefly the process producing the spray agglomerates of interest. Then we describe, how image information from XCT offline data of agglomerates is used to establish a correlation between the 2D fractal dimension and the shape descriptor Roundness (R) of that agglomerate. In the final step, we show how to transition from 2D fractal dimension to 3D fractal dimension.

Spray fluidized bed agglomeration: Process setup

We briefly summarize the experimental setup and conditions that generates the aggregates used in this study as described in Ajalova et al. (2024). For a detailed description of the agglomerate formation process and the influence of the operation parameters binder spray rate, primary particle feed rate, gas inlet temperature and binder solids mass fraction, we refer to Ajalova et al. (2024).

A pilot scale cylindrical fluidized bed with an inner diameter of 300 mm was used with continuous primary particle feed and a non-classifying outlet located in the center of the distributor plate.

A two-fluid spray nozzle (Düsen-Schlick GmbH, model 940/6 with a hemispheric cap, liquid orifice diameter: 0.8 mm) was used to spray the binder solution onto the fluidized particles. The binder solution consists of water to which different mass fractions of hydroxy-propyl-methyl-cellulose (HPMC, trade name: Pharmacoat 606 from Shin-Etsu, Japan) were added. In all experiments, an atomization flow rate of $0.08 \text{ m}^3 (\text{air}) \text{ min}^{-1}$ and a binder feed rate of 32 g min^{-1} were realized. For fluidization, air was provided with a mass flow rate of approximately 280 kg h^{-1} .

Primary particles were transparent glass beads with a mass density of 2500 kg m^{-3} and an average diameter (volume-based) of 0.24 mm.

Variations in process dynamics were studied with respect to gas inlet temperature (influencing the drying and solidification of the liquid bridges) and the weight fraction of HPMC in the binder solution (influencing probability of agglomeration of particles on collision and mechanical strength of the formed solid bridges). Table 1 collects the experimental parameters of all case studies. All experiments were run for 120 minutes; samples were taken from the process chamber every ten minutes.

Offline data evaluation: 3D and image information from X-Ray μ -computed tomography

The X-ray tomograph used in this study was a customized device (CT Procon alpha 2000 by ProCon X-ray GmbH, Garbsen, Germany). The X-ray source was operated at 40 kV and $80 \text{ }\mu\text{A}$. The agglomerate to be investigated was placed around 655 mm from the detector. By rotation of the sample holder, each agglomerate was scanned in the

entire range of 0° – 360° in 1200 rotation steps. The increment of angle change was 0.3° , with an exposure time of 1 s each. Total acquisition time per agglomerate time was about 1 h. The voxel size of the reconstructed volume is $3.5\ \mu\text{m}$ in each direction.

Correlating agglomerate roundness R to 2D fractal dimension

The angle-dependent images of an agglomerate obtained from the X-ray tomograph were evaluated with respect to shape descriptors and the 2D fractal dimension. After image acquisition, in a pre-processing step the image brightness was adjusted and measurement noise removed. This is followed by a binarization of the image data, using Otsu's method, and inversion of brightness high and low level. After this procedure, background is represented by black, the agglomerate in white (Fig. 2).

For a given image, the roundness R of an individual agglomerate is computed as:

$$R = \frac{4A}{\pi x_{\max}^2}, \quad (1)$$

where A is the projected area of the agglomerate (obtained by counting the number of white pixels), and x_{\max} corresponds to the maximum cord length within the agglomerate. The selection of R as shape factor was motivated by earlier work of Arasan et al. (2011). Other measures, e.g., circularity, were tried as well but showed insufficient sensitivity to observed results.

Two-dimensional (2D) fractal dimension $D_{f,2D}$ is obtained in an iterative process via box counting as described in Walsh and Watterson (1993). Herein, smaller and smaller boxes are overlaid on top of the outline of the agglomerate. The number of boxes from one iteration to the next, together with the degree of coverage, converges to the 2D fractal dimension.

Typical evaluation times for roundness R and 2D fractal dimension by box counting are 5 ms and 200 ms (averages per agglomerate), respectively.

Due to the general anisotropy of agglomerates, roundness and fractal dimension are angle dependent, i.e., their values depend on the orientation under which they are observed. Although this is no issue when using 3D characterization methods, like XCT techniques, it is challenging in an online 2D setup as the angle is unknown and cannot be controlled.

Figure 3 exemplifies this for agglomerates taken from experiments A and E. As can be seen there is a significant difference between the two experiments as well as with respect to the variation within one experiment. Main reason for the variation within one set of experimental conditions is that not all agglomerates are formed exactly the same, e.g., some may undergo subsequent breakage due to fluidization. The variation with respect to angle is due to random spatial integration or attachment of new primary particles to an existing agglomerate.

For that reason, for each agglomerate, the angle-averaged values of R and $D_{f,2D}$ are used in the following.

Correlating 2D fractal dimension to 3D fractal dimension of spray agglomerates

Based on 2D fractal dimension $D_{f,2D}$, the 3D fractal dimension of spray agglomerates can be estimated (Wang et al. 2022):

$$D_{f,PL} = 0.2015 D_{f,2D}^{4.079} \quad (2)$$

The 3D fractal dimension of a spray agglomerate $D_{f,PL}$ is expressed by the power law. Further information that can be inferred from this value are, e.g., number of primary particles N_p in the agglomerate and the agglomerate porosity (Wang et al. 2022).

The step-wise approach has now linked the shape factor roundness (R) to the 3D fractal dimension $D_{f,PL}$. The data sets of all experiments are shown in Fig. 4 (color-coded) and overlaid by a regression line:

$$D_{f,PL} = 0.651 R + 1.629 . \quad (3)$$

This correlation, the main result of this contribution, allows for fast online estimation of 3D fractal dimension, as only two simple algebraic operation have to be added to the online evaluation procedure. Consequently, the average evaluation time for both, R and $D_{f,PL}$, combined is still 5 ms. It has to be noted that the regression line covers all data points; there are, however, some influences of the operating conditions on the slope and intercept of the regression line. These offer the opportunity to correlate the slope and intercept as functions of the gas temperature and the binder weight fraction. For the sake of simplicity of the expression (Eq. 3), this is not pursued here.

Results and discussion

In the following, we present some exemplary results of the characterization scheme for the conditions reported in Tab. 1.

Online data source: High speed image acquisition

Agglomerates were produced in the spray fluidized bed according to the operation parameters reported in Tab. 1. To avoid problems with illumination and synchronization of agglomerate feed to the image acquisition, the whole feeding and image acquisition is performed within a Camsizer (MicrotracRetsch). For image acquisition, a high-speed camera (framerate 60 fps at a resolution of 768 pixels (height) by 1012 pixels (width), grayscale color space) is used. Related to the field of view, a spatial resolution of 15 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ is achieved in both directions.

Periodically (every ten minutes), a sample is diverted from the fluidized bed to the measurement equipment. Via a vibrating chute, transport of the agglomerates towards a shaft is realized. Once, agglomerates enter the shaft, they attain their free fall velocity and pass a uniformly illuminated plane where the images are taken. The images are processed as described earlier; agglomerate features are extracted and the corresponding property distributions are generated. Typical sample amounts result in feeding times of about 3 to 5 minutes. Table 2 presents the number of agglomerates evaluated per experiment and sampling event. At least 100 agglomerates are evaluated per time step using the new correlation (Eq. 3), with a maximum exceeding 1000 agglomerates – unprecedented numbers compared to traditional techniques.

Selected results

Figure 5 presents the distribution of fractal dimension across all experimental conditions after spray agglomeration for 120 minutes. Also shown are fitted normal distributions with the same mean and standard deviation as obtained from the samples. Two groups of experimental conditions can be observed by comparison with the mean 3D fractal dimension: Experiments A and E make up one group, and experiments B, C and D make up a second group, but without any drastic changes in the property distribution.

Figures 6 and 7 present the distribution of $D_{f,PL}$ for experiments A and E, respectively, as functions of time. In both cases, a non-normal distribution is generated by the particle formulation process. This is evidenced by the overlaid normal distribution with the same mean value and standard deviation as the sample distribution. Noticeable in both property distributions is the presence of two modes: The mode in the range 2.2—2.3 corresponds to the presence of primary particles that are very spherical (but not perfect); the mode around 2.0 then corresponds to the dominant agglomerate size fraction.

Under the conditions of experiment A (cf. Tab. 1, Fig. 6), fractal dimension ranges between 1.7 and 2.3 for all times. However, within these ranges, over process time a shift towards smaller values is observed (e.g., by comparison of the mean values of the overlaid normal distribution). This corresponds to the experience that initially, the total sample is still dominated by the primary particles that are very spherical. With decreasing number of primary particles, more complex (i.e., fractal) structures are formed. After about 20 minutes, the distribution of fractal dimension stabilizes within the process, i.e., a dynamic equilibrium between attachment and detachment of additional primary particles and smaller clusters to agglomerates is achieved.

A similar observation holds for agglomerates formulated under the conditions of experiment E (Fig. 7): Here also a shift from higher to lower values signals the formation of more complex structures, with overall values ranging between 1.7 and 2.3 as well. Different to experiment A, the stabilization of fractal dimension is achieved at a later stage within the process (about 50 min.), but with a similar average value. The different dynamic behavior is a consequence of the different thermal conditions. The thermal conditions (gas inlet temperature and binder content in spray) influence the probabilities of successful wetting of a primary particle with the binder and of successful incorporation of a primary particle into a larger structure. Furthermore, the mechanical strength of the solidified bridges between neighboring particles in an agglomerate differ due to the thermal condition during solidification, resulting in different breakage behavior of the agglomerate due to fluid shear force and collision forces (agglomerate-agglomerate or agglomerate-apparatus collisions).

This shows that with under different operation conditions the same product properties can be achieved. This opens the door to process optimization with respect to

ecological or economic cost measures, e.g., minimum consumption of energy for heating of gas or use of binder.

Furthermore, investigating the particle size distribution of all five experiments (Fig. 8), differences in the particle size distribution of the agglomerates can be observed: Experiments B, C and D exhibit a very similar distribution of fractal dimension compared to experiments A and E (in shape but with a shifted mean value); however, the corresponding size distributions are significantly different. This highlights the potential of fluidized bed spray agglomeration to design agglomerated product with a defined application profile.

Conclusions and outlook

A model-based inference procedure for the fast online assessment of 3D fractal dimension of agglomerates formulated in spray fluidized beds has been developed and implemented. Compared to other evaluation techniques, unprecedented numbers of agglomerates can be characterized, even fulfilling hard real-time constraints, such as those required in feedback control schemes.

This procedure generates new insights into the dynamics of structure formation that can be used in process control for rational design of agglomerated products.

Further improvements can be achieved by correlating the parameters of the R - $D_{f,PL}$ correlation to typical operation conditions, e.g., gas inlet temperature and binder weight fraction.

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Table 1. Experimental parameters of spray fluidized bed agglomeration trials performed by (Ajalova et al. 2024). For parameters kept constant across all experiments, see text.

	A	B	C	D	E
Inlet gas temperature / °C	80	90	100	90	90
Binder content / wt-%	4	4	4	2	6
Particle feed rate / g min ⁻¹	145	158	182	166	155

Table 2. Number of identified objects per measurement cycle. No significant change after 60 min is observed (equilibrium of agglomerate formation and breakup).

Time point	A	B	C	D	E
0 min	3156	3156	3156	3156	3156
10 min	1103	91	402	1187	594
20 min	568	203	393	1131	748
50 min	743	114	261	938	450
60 min	676	148	486	1067	373

Figure 1. General scheme of structure formation in spray agglomeration

Figure 2. Effect of image pre-processing. a) Image obtained from X-ray μ -computed tomography (single angle view); b) after noise removal and binarization.

Figure 3. Exemplified angle dependency of shape factor for spray agglomerates due to their general anisotropy (left: experiment A (N = 3), right: experiment E (N = 8)).

Figure 4. Roundness vs 3D fractal dimension of spray agglomerates evaluated from offline X-ray μ -CT images. Over all experiments, 455 pairs of data have been evaluated from 35 unique agglomerates. Overlaid is the linear regression line expressing 3D fractal dimension as function of agglomerate roundness R .

Figure 5. Distribution of fractal dimension across all experimental conditions after 120 minutes of fluidized bed spray agglomeration.

Figure 6. Evolution of distribution of fractal dimension with time (Experiment A).

Figure 7. Evolution of distribution of fractal dimension with time (Experiment E).

Figure 8. Agglomerate size distribution across all experimental conditions after 120 minutes of processing (steady state, i.e., dynamic equilibrium achieved after max. 60 minutes in all cases).